

EVOLUTION OF PRECONDITIONS OF INTEGRATION OF NATIVE ENTERPRISES IN THE WORLD ECONOMY: THEORETICAL QUESTIONS

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Abstract

Studies of evolution of preconditions of native enterprises integration in the world economy are urgent, taking into account the fact that unevenness of evolution of both sustainable and technological development was fixed in Ukraine.

The aim of the article is to determine and to substantiate evolution of preconditions of integration of native enterprises in the world economy for improving provision of the economic stability and development.

The theoretical-methodological base of the article is scientific works of native and foreign scientists on problematic of integration of native enterprises in the world economy. The general approaches and research methods have been used at preparing the article: theoretical generalization, historical, analysis, synthesis and abstraction.

The use of these methods allowed to note that the process of establishment of the economic block of Ukrainian legislation cannot be considered as finished for today, the factor of production functioning and development is in the base of the civilized development of mankind, development of native enterprises must be more distinctly oriented on taking into account the evolution factor in forms and tendencies of the world economic development, rates of integration of native enterprises in international production networks are conditioned by rates and scale of establishing the system of correspondent standardized preconditions.

It has been explained, that the lag in adaptation of the native standards system of the international and European ones takes place that is an important obstacle at entering of native enterprises in the world economy. That is why it is extremely important in the context of sustainable development to provide evenness in production standardization processes.

An essential attention at the study has been paid to the importance of most effective means of quality management, especially standardization of documentary principles of management. Just entering of Ukraine to the World trade organization must activate this process, because the fund of native standards includes several ten times less documents that in developed countries.

Keywords: evolution, preconditions, integration, production, standards, quality, management, Ukraine.

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1. Introduction

It is impossible to imagine modern civilization processes without production ones. In his time Plato indicated that production is managed by science for its correct realization, and art manages everything that is produced [1, p. 169, 183]. Then these theses were elaborated by Xenophons in the process of development of the general economic ideology on bases of works that people realize for their benefit [2, p. 128]. Aristotle made an important step in studying the production factor, having separated an essential and role participation of qualitative and quantitative production components in it [3, p. 155].

Philosophical understanding of the production essence in old times was, undoubtedly, too abstract for making it really useful for real workers. Efforts of scientists of the New Epoch were directed on overcoming this abstractness. Thus, A. Smith discovered the very essence of concrete

production, realized by separate enterprises, and their mutual connections both within a state and at the international level. From his point of view each human, having accepted local conditions, may judge better than any statesman or legislator about just what type of native industry to apply own capital to, and a product of what industry may have the most cost. That is why law must always allow people to care about own interests themselves, because they are able to judge about their special conditions and positions usually better than a legislator [4, p. 443, 508].

In certain time I. Kant supported the thesis of A. Smith as to more freedom of activity: when one impedes a citizen to build own prosperity by a chosen method, accordant with freedom of others, one deprives the whole production of life activity, in such a way decreases a force of the whole. But the mentioned freedom of a producer, according to I. Kant, creates preconditions for realization of its highest purpose, after a series of some transforming revolutions, planned by nature – the general world-civic state as a bosom, where all initial inclinations of the human family develop [5, p. 25, 26].

Globalization of the modern world, as D. Held and other scientists state it, it is “one of ideas, about which we can state that their time has come” and it “must be understood as a process that embodies transformation of the space organization of social relations and interactions, measured by such parameters as their duration, intensity, speed and effect, and generates intercontinental or interregional flows (shifts of physical artifacts, people, symbols, signs and information though time and space) and structures of activity, interactions and power manifestations [6, p. 47, 56].

But representatives of the Roman club, A. King and B. Snyder, indicate on topicality of introducing the “common approach to global problems”, where an important place is occupied by the “necessity of general standard, principles for coordinated actions and thousands of other technical agreements” [7, p. 35, 36]. According to the definition by D. Stiglits, “globalization - the elimination of barriers to free trade and closer integration of native economies – may be a good force and has a potential for making every one on the world richer”, synchronously taking into account “provision of the transfer to new standards and norms, accepted in leading industrial countries of the world” [8, p. 16; 9, p. 270.].

The system of state management of entrepreneurial activity in Ukraine underwent the long stage of evolution and varied depending on economic growth rates and economic policy vector. At the same time under conditions of external trade liberalization, the rate of integration of native enterprises in international economic networks is conditioned by rates and scales of establishing the system of correspondent standardized preconditions. Despite essential achievements of economic science in studying evolution of preconditions of native enterprises integration in the world economy, many questions remain open.

2. Aim of research

The main aim of the research is to define evolution of preconditions of native enterprises integration in the world economy.

3. Materials and methods

In this article the analysis is limited by discussion of theoretical aspects of native enterprises integration in the world economy using the methods of theoretical generalization, analysis, synthesis and abstraction.

In any economy an enterprise is its key link. The essence of the notion “enterprise” was defined by a series of scientists (**Table 1**).

It must be noted, that market evolution of enterprises in Ukraine originated from soviet principles of their formation, defined in 1990 by the Law No. 1529 «On enterprises in USSR», where article 1 stated that an enterprise:

1) is an independent economic subject with rights of a juridical person, that produces and realizes products, based on using a property by a labor staff, make works, gives services, doesn't include other juridical persons, not depending on forms of property category on production means and other property, acts on principles of economic calculation;

2) its main tasks are to satisfy social needs in its products, works and services and realization of social and economic interests of a labor staff and owners of an enterprise's property, based on gained profit;

3) can realize any types of economic activity, not prohibited by legislative acts within statute aims.

Table 1

Theoretical definition of the category "enterprise"

Scientists-economists	Content definition
V. Zombart	Enterprise (in the widest sense) means any existence of a far-seeing plan, for which realization a long-term activity of several persons, subjected to a unitary will is needed [10, p. 44]
K. R. Mconnell, S. L. Bru	Enterprise is a certain material structure (factory, plant, firm, mine, wholesale shop, warehouse and so on) that realizes one or several functions on production and distribution of goods and services [11, p. 87]
I. A. Blank	Enterprise as an open socio-economic system, able to self-organization. This principle of strategic management is in fact that at elaborating a financial strategy, an enterprise is considered as a certain system, completely open for active interaction with factors of the external environment [12, p. 26]
V. G. Andriychuk	Enterprise is a main organizationally separated and economically independent link of market economy that produces goods (gives services correspondingly to the demand for them and available economic resources) [13, p. 25]

We can see, that point 2 of article 1 of the Law No. 1529 unambiguously concentrates activity of enterprises on realizing a function of satisfying social needs in certain products, works, services that makes it extremely dependent on a state regulation form. If address to the content of table 2, the Law of Ukraine of 1991 (No. 887) doesn't already contain this function, and enterprises are oriented on activity for getting a correspondent profit (income). But point 3 of article 1 states, that in a case of unprofitable activity the state gives them a guarantee as to their support (subsidies, other privileges), if their products was preliminarily accepted as socially necessary.

With introduction of the Economic code of Ukraine in 2004 that absorbed the Ukrainian Law No. 887, we don't already see the aim of "getting a correspondent profit (income)" in the definition of enterprise". "For satisfying social and personal needs" appeared at its place, that more reminds of the definition of 1990 (social needs are at the first place, and personal – at the second one, that is subjected to first ones). It is also expedient here to indicate that point 5 of article 11 of the Economic code of Ukraine provides a possibility of giving economic subjects subsidies and privileges, provided by the law, for realizing their economic activity under conditions of taking into account social interests, presented in actual program documents of the economic and social development, by them. So, the process of market establishment of the economic block of Ukrainian legislation cannot be considered as finished in its final look yet (**Table 2**).

At the end of XX – beginning of XXI century the question of integration in the world economy and euro-integration were activated in Ukraine. In 1998 the Law of the President Of Ukraine No. 615 accepted the Strategy of integration of Ukraine to the European Union, where was provided the gradual adaptation of the Ukrainian legislation to European standards that includes custom, private, labor, financial, tax legislation, one of intellectual property, labor protection, life and health protection, protection of consumers' rights, external natural environment, technical rules and standards, transport and other branches, defined by the Agreement about partnership and cooperation (of 1994). As a development of the above mentioned Strategy, the Order of the President of Ukraine No. 1072 of 2000 accepted the program of the Integration of Ukraine to the European Union, which priorities of creation conditions as to gaining membership of Ukraine in EU included, in the first turn, coordinated realization of key organization-economic and normative-legal arrangements that would provide the future approximation to EU standards.

Table 2
Legislative definitions of the category “enterprise”

Law of Ukraine	Content of definition
On enterprises in Ukraine. Law of Ukraine of 27 of March of 1991 No. 887-XII	<p>Article 1. Enterprise and its main aims:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enterprise is an organizational link of the national economy of Ukraine. Enterprise is an independent economic statute subject that has rights of juridical person and realizes production, research and commercial activity for getting a correspondent profit (income). 2. An enterprise realizes any types of economic activity, if they are not prohibited by Ukrainian legislation and correspond to aims, provided by the statute of an enterprise. 3. In a case of unprofitable activity the state gives enterprises subsidies, other privileges, if it accepts their products as socially necessary
Economic code of Ukraine. Ukrainian law of 16.01.2003 No. 436-IV	<p>Article 62. Enterprise as an organizational economic form:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enterprise is an independent economic subject, created by a competent body of the state power of local self-government, or other subjects for satisfying social and personal needs by systematic realization of production, research, trade, other economic activity in order, provided by this Code and other laws. 2. Enterprises can be created for both realization of entrepreneurship and non-commercial economic activity

According to requirements of the Strategy and program of integration of Ukraine to EU, studies of key aspects of this question become activate in Ukraine. Thus, for example, the studies of V.S. Ponomarenko have proved that the development of native enterprises must be more distinctly oriented at taking into account the factor of evolution in forms and tendencies of the world economic development [14].

The importance of deeper standardization of the activity of enterprises (aspect of organization of anti-crisis management taking into account national and international requirements and standards) is indicated by the studies by L. O. Ligonenko[15].

The studies of O. O. Tereschenko have established the urgency of improving the state policy of supporting financial sanitation of enterprises and its harmonization with EU standards as to economic competition protection [16].

The studies of O. L. Kanischenko have proved that at the modern development stage of world integration processes there form such unique managerial mechanisms that organically combine world standards of marketing activity and ethnocentral originality of native management systems [17].

The studies of O. I. Momot have established, that for introducing modern international standards at enterprises for systems of their management, the preparatory work with the population is needed; it mainly concerns the terminology in the sphere of managing the quality, standardization and certification [18].

The studies by T. V. Orekhova testify to the fact that a manifestation of integration of economic systems at the microlevel and a result of their internationalization are the process of transnationalization that correspondingly provides taking into account the effect of five standardized (by international standard systems) variables: production volumes of a company, volume of export of its products, pure profit of a company, expenditures for SRCW by a company, volume of its own capital [19].

The studies of N. P. Nishenko have proved the urgency of introducing common world standards of accounting and financial reporting that gives a possibility to eliminate economic and trade barriers, to activate foreign investments, to enter world capital markets, to form the competitive market environment for enterprises [20].

The studies by S. S. Olejnikova have revealed that taking into account the active participation of Ukraine in international trade, the development of standardization and certification systems, based on principles, methods and functions that provide most advanced international and interstate norms, becomes extremely important [21].

The studies by A. A. Pilipenko have discovered just potential possibilities of organization of management of the integration development of economic subjects that create preconditions for re-

alizing the model of their cluster-network interaction, based on the effective regulation of dynamic functioning standards [22].

The studies of I. Y. Zvarych have established the urgency of including Ukrainian enterprises in production networks of Europe as a subcontract that deepens the international labor distribution, in such a way allowing to solve existent problems of partners, partially at the expense of spreading innovations, but at that it is necessary to coordinate interests of countries-partners in the context of the existent normative-legal environment of their activity [23].

So, rates of integration of native enterprises in international production networks are conditioned by rates and scale of establishing the system of correspondent standardized preconditions. Just this correspondence is aimed by the “Agreement on association between Ukraine on the one side and European Union and its countries-members – on the other” (below – the Agreement on association between Ukraine and EU), ratified by the Law of Ukraine of 2014 No. 1678-VII.

Alongside with it, it must be noted, that formation of the system of standardized preconditions of integration of native enterprises in international production networks is realized unevenly in time and in the aspect of types of normative acts. This thesis is well illustrated on the example of classification acts (**Table 3**). There must be underlined that the presented key classifications are in fact international ones, adapted to Ukrainian conditions. Thus, SC 003 «Classifier of occupations» was elaborated based on ISCO-88: International Standard Classification of Occupations / ILO, Geneva of 1988, that the International conference of labor statistics, International bureau of labor recommended for transferring national data in a system that simplifies the international exchange of professional information. SC 009 «Classification of types of economic activities» was elaborated based on Nomenclature of Activities European Community (NACE, Rev.1, mod.7) and so on.

At the same time it must be indicated that introduction of, for example, Classification of institutional sectors of Ukrainian economy (CISUE) in a certain way strengthens the system of usual and commonly accepted notions in Ukraine, taking into account that a generalizing term for economic communities in CISUE is accepted as corporations (institutional organizations, created just for market production of goods and services and are sources of profit or other financial benefits for their owners (in market economy corporations are considered as a main institutional form of entrepreneurship). Accordingly, private non-financial corporations include economic subjects (COLFE) of agriculture, private and collective entrepreneurship, joint-stock of different responsibility forms, cooperatives, associations, corporations, consortiums, concerns, holding companies.

It is known, that in 70–80's of XX century there developed the process of searching for most effective methods of managing the quality, and TQM (Total Quality Management) was formulated, where, as A. Feinbaum put it, four stages were separated:

- 1) elaboration of standards;
- 2) estimation of responsibility;
- 3) use of necessary arrangements;
- 4) planning of arrangements as to improving elaborated standards [24, p. 38].

That is this process of TQM introduction coincided with the process of production standardization under conditions of accelerated changes in innovation and information spheres. Certain efforts towards the improvement of these systems were undertaken in Ukraine too.

The correspondent Laws of Ukraine were accepted in the sphere of standardization for this reason: On metrology and metrological activity (No. 113, 1998); On confirmation of correspondence (No. 2406, 2001); On accreditation of authorities on responsibility estimation (No. 2407, 2001); On standardization (No. 2408, 2001; No. 1315, 2014); On standards, technical regulations and procedures of responsibility estimation (No. 3164, 2005); On technical regulations and responsibility estimation (No. 124, 2015). The Law of Ukraine No. 124 distinctly determines that the module of responsibility estimation is a unified procedure of estimating responsibility or its part, determined according to the correspondent act of EU legislation. At that it is important that the aim of standardization and main principles of state policy in the sphere of standardization (art. 4 of Ukrainian Law No. 1315) is support of rational production, life and health protection; rights and interests of consumers, safety of labor, preservation of the external natural environment and saving

of all resource types, elimination of technical barriers in trade and prevention of their appearance, support of the development and international competitiveness of products, adaptation to modern achievements of science and technique, favoring of introduction of innovations and competitiveness of products of native producers, priority of acceptance of international and regional codes of stable practice as national ones in Ukraine, participation in international and regional standardization and so on.

Table 3

Succession of introduction of classifiers in Ukraine

Year	Classification
1994	SC 001 Classification of property forms (CPF) SC 002 Classification of organizational-legal forms of economy (COLFE) General classifier of “Branches of national economy” (GCBNE)
1995	SC 003 Classifier of occupations (CO)
1996	SC 005 Classifier of wastes (CW)
1997	SC 011 Classifier of designation system of measuring and accounting units (CDSMAU) SC 012 Classifier of services of external economic activity (CSEEA) SC 013 Classification of main funds (CMF) SC 014 Classifier of objects of administrative-territorial order of Ukraine SC 015 Classification of types of scientific-technical activity (CTSTA) SC016 State classifier of products and services
1998	SC 006 Classifier of foreign currencies and bank metals (CFCBM) SC 010 State classifier of managerial documents (SCMD)
1999	SC 017 Ukrainian classification of external economic activity
2000	SC 018 State classifier of buildings and facilities
2001	SC 201 Classification of services and consumer servicing
2003	SC 004 Ukrainian classifier of normative documents (UCND)
2005	Classification of institutional sectors of Ukrainian economy (CISUE) SC 009 Classification of types of economic activity (CTEA)
2007	SC 008 Classifier of useful minerals (CUM)
2010	SC 019 State classifier of emergencies

Certain efforts were also made in the native sphere of innovatization based on the accepted Laws of Ukraine: On special regime of investment and innovative activity of technological parks (No. 991, 1999); On innovative activity (No. 40-IVof 4 July of 2002); On priority directions of innovative activity in Ukraine (No. 433, 2003; No. 3715, 2011); On state regulation of activity in the sphere of transfer of technologies (No. 143 of 14 September of 2006). But any essential shifts in the innovative sphere didn't take place. The organization of the economic cooperation and development (OECD) elaborated the typical model of the National innovative system (NIS), widely used in developed countries of the world, already in 1997. But only in 2007 Verhovna Rada of Ukraine accepted the decision On Recommendations of parliamentary hearing on the theme: «National innovative system of Ukraine: problems of formation and realization» (No. 1244), that indicates that a final result of the development of science and high-technological branches in XX century was the formation of the new mechanism of self-development in economies of leading countries – national innovative systems (below – NIS), here innovations originate and develop, and the common features of all NIS without exclusions is leadership in providing three development priorities: science, education and high-technological production. And as opposite to these countries, Ukraine has not already created NIS, so its innovative activity is characterized with structural deformation, institutional incompleteness, discordance and unbalance of technological, economic and socio-value aspects. For overcoming obstacles on the way of Ukrainian NIS,

there were provided arrangements, among which already during 2007 – I half-year of 2008 there must be started pilot projects as to creation of innovatively oriented consortiums that would unite leading native technical universities, scientific institutions, enterprises, financial institutions with further formation of stable innovative clusters on this base. Unfortunately, such projects have not been realized till today. And already in 2018 the decision of Verhovna Rada No. 2291 On realization of parliamentary hearing on the theme: “National innovative system: condition and legislative support of development” was accepted, but this hearing has not taken place till today.

In the sphere of informatization a situation reminds of one in innovatization: in 1998 two important Laws of Ukraine were accepted – On National program of informatization (No. 74) and On Conception of the National program of informatization (No. 75), and in 2007– On main development principles of information society in Ukraine for 2007–2015 years (No. 537). But for today realization of statements of these laws is obviously stoped. There must be reminded, that the Okinawa charter of Global information society (GIS) stated already in 2000 that the international support of countries must be coordinated with their ability to work in GIS completely. It was confirmed by the National information society policy (NISP), elaborated in 2003 in EU.

Let’s underline that the Law of Ukraine No. 537 provided: in first, transfer to the priority scientific-technical and innovative development; in second, coordination and consolidation of efforts of the state, business and society for the development of information society in Ukraine; in third, coordination of programs (national branch, regional) and business-projects in the sphere of new information-communicative technologies in-fourth, correspondence of e-information resources to standards and technical regulations, national, branch and local classifiers and so on. So, realization of statements of this Law of Ukraine would allow to solve the complex of problems of science and production, standardization and innovatization systematically.

4. Results

So, the lag in adaptation of the native standards system to international and European ones takes place in Ukraine. It is understood, that it is a powerful brake on the way of native enterprises to their inclusion in the world economy. There is to the point to remind, that the State standardization program for 2006-2010 (accepted by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministries of Ukraine No. 229, 2006) accented the determining role of standardization in providing production of competitive and high-quaity products, environment protection, resource-saving, and at the same time indicated that the standardization system of Ukraine doesn’t correspond to international requirements as to realization of international trade through using an essential number of normative documents of the former USSR, non-observance of actual requirements SSU ISO/IEC Guide 59:2000 “Code of stable rules of standardization”.

The entering of Ukraine into the World trade organization (WTO), undoubtedly, would activate attention to standardization of documentary principles of management [25, p. 147]. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministries of Ukraine No. 228 (2006) states, that the fund of native standards includes ten times less documents than in developed countries yet. Instead of it, WOT actively interacts with the sphere of international standardization, including ISO, and with one of informatization. Already in 1994WOT accepted the decision as to approval of the offered agreement on informational system of standards WTO-ISO: ISONET [26].

If address to the base standard SSU ISO 9000 – 2001 System of quality management (**Table 4**), it becomes clear that none enterprise can enter the world productivity and effectiveness level of processes without the system use of approaches, offered in this standard, including in the first turn: procedural, aim and policy, strategical role of the highest management and so on. It is appropriately to remind highest leaders that according to the Typical instrction on record keeping (decision of the Cabinet of Ministries of Ukraine No. 1242 (2011), their managers are responsible for record keeping organization in institutions. It is understood, that under conditions of such information exploision that accompanes the modern economic development, none manager is able to provide the full-value movement of documents without using modern standards (such as ISO/TR 15489-2, ISO/IEC 15288), adapted to requirements of high information technologies.

Table 4
Succession of introducing standards of series ISO and EN in Ukraine

Year	Standards
2001	Code of stable rules of standardization. SSU ISO/IEC Guide 59-2000 SSUIISO 9000 – 2001 Systems of quality management. Main statements and vocabulary Safety of machines. Main notions. General designing principles. SSU EN 292-1: 2001
2003	Rules and methods of acceptance and use of international and regional standards. SSU 1.7-2001. (ISO/IEC Guide 21: 1999, NEQ) Instructions on elaborating documents for quality management systems. SSU ISO/TR 10013: 2003 Safety aspects. Instructions as to their inclusion to standards (ISO/IEC Guide 51: 1999, IDT). SSUIISO/IEC Guide 51-2002
2005	Information and documents. Management of documentary processes SSU 4423: 2005 (ISO/TR 15489-2) Instructions as to quality managements in projects SSU ISO 10006: 2005 Safety of machines; Physical possibilities of humans SSU EN 1005-1: 2005
2006	System of ecological management. Requirements and instructions as to use (SSU ISO 14001:2006) System of safety and labor hygiene management. Requirements of SSU-P OHSAS 18001: 2006
2007	Information technologies. Processes of the system life cycle (ISO/IEC 15288: 2002, IDT) SSU ISO/IEC 15288: 2005 System of food products safety management. Requirements to any organizations of the food chain (ISO 22000: 2005, IDT) SSUIISO 22000: 2007 Not translated in Ukraine
X	Risk-management (ISO 31000:2009)
X	Management of social responsibility (ISO 26000:2010)

For improving the quality management system, managers must master methods of estimation of processes, subjected to them, identify their correspondence to the potential, prepare the system for external audit by ISO 19011, systematic estimation of suitability, adequacy and effectiveness of the quality management system basing on the policy and aims in the quality sphere, provide the internal self-estimation of the organization for timely neutralization of risks.

For today the sustainable development management (harmonic coordination of social, ecological and economic components of production activity) is a development paradigm of all countries of the world. Bases of the sustainable development of Ukraine are contained in its Constitution that accepted a human as the highest social value (art. 3) and prohibited to use property (and also resources) to the detriment of a human or society (art. 13), acknowledged provision of ecological safety and support of ecological balance at the territory of Ukraine together with preservation of the gene pool of its nation as a duty, and its economic safety – as the most important function of the state (art. 16 and 17). The Law of Ukraine “On bases of national safety” (No. 964, 2003) acknowledged the urgency of providing the sustainable development of the state, where timely revelation, prevention and neutralization of potential threats to national interests must be provided just by the adaptation of Ukrainian laws to EU ones [27, p. 18].

In the context of sustainable development it becomes extremely urgent to provide evenness in processes of production standardization, because each component of the standards system must be coordinated with other ones. For example, standards ISO 9000 are directed on improving mainly production (economic) activity parameters, standards ISO 14000 – on the natural environment (ecology), and SSU-P OHSAS 18001, ISO 26000 and so on – on social aspects of activity. Essential discordances can appear because of a series of objective circumstances. On the one side, the economic block of national production is regulated by native legal acts on taxes, protection of economic competition, economic regime, property, insurance and so on. On the other one, Ukraine accepted standards of international financial organization, World trade organization, European economic commission of UNO, FAO, UNIDO and so on. On the one side, the ecological block of national production is regulated by native legal acts on protection of the natural external environment, on emissions, ecological audit and ecological assessment. On the other side, Ukraine signed numerous

international acts, among which the World charter of nature, Frame conception of UNO on climate changes, Rio Declaration on external environment and development, Ecological program for Europe and so on. On the one side, the social block of national production is regulated by native legal acts on state social standards and state social guarantees, labor payment, population employment, labor protection and so on. On the other side, Ukraine signed numerous international acts, among which the General declaration of human rights, Declaration of social progress and development of UNO, European social charter, Declarations, conventions and recommendations of the international labor organization and so on. The thorough modern standardization of production processes must be directed just on sufficient coordination of internal (native) and external (international) legal acts; it allows to provide the growth of the specific weight of enterprises that will win a place at world markets effectively.

The analysis of the Agreement of Association between Ukraine and EU, ratified in 2014, gives grounds to state that the economic integration of Ukraine into EU market (with creating the free trade zone in approximately 10 years from the moment of signing the Agreement) needs the use of principles of sustainable development and green economy, adaptation and application of technical regulations, standards and works on estimating the responsibility (Chapter 3 on Technical barriers in trade) taking into account requirements of innovative shifts and information society. In 2017 the volume of double-sided trade between Ukraine and EU grew by 29 % that was achieved mainly by arrangements, provided by the Agreement on association for the sphere of technical barriers in trade. Especially there were introduced acts of European vertical (sectoral) legislation in 27 sectors of production industry. At the same time effective rules and methods were introduced in the part of registration and activity of companies for improving the entrepreneurial climate.

5. Conclusions

1. The factor of production functioning and development lays in the base of civilized development of mankind, at that it is important to determine a measure of freedom of actions of separate producers and degree of their subordination to social interests at each development stage for any society; it will further determine a ratio of integration and differential tendencies.

2. The modern world labor distribution (globalization) forms correspondent criteria of full-value preconditions of development of producers of concrete goods and services, based only on local possibilities of territories; that is participation in international production networks becomes an objective need of native enterprises.

3. The inclusion of any national enterprise in international production networks needs coordination of requirements to these goods and services that can be potentially made by this producer, in another case there appears a contradiction between demand and supply that blocks the movement of values between two sides that is just the determining motive of standards creation.

4. At the modern stage of world economic standardization its coordination with processes of the general technological development (innovatization, informatization) becomes more urgent that essentially increases the level of requirements to the quality of production systems management, especially taking into account requirements of their sustainable development (harmonization of social, economic and ecological).

5. Ukraine demonstrates the unevenness of evolution of components of both sustainable and technological development. It generates correspondent negative results and needs searching for mechanisms that will help to determine characteristics of the harmony of the aforesaid components, on which base their effective management for taking them into the desirable condition will be possible.

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